

Our Community, Our Impact
MetaDocencia 2025

MetaDocencia

LEE LA VERSIÓN EN ESPAÑOL AQUÍ

Founded in 2020, MetaDocencia is a community rooted across Latin America with global reach—connecting researchers, educators, and organizations to benefit science worldwide.

MetaDocencia unlocks Latin America's extraordinary scientific talent for the world.

We strengthen infrastructure, training, and community support, removing barriers to amplify the impact of Latin American researchers and their participation in global science.

In five years, we have strengthened a scientific network of **2,000+** professionals, worked with **30+** communities, trained **1,600+** people, connected **6,000+**, and published **200+** resources on Zenodo.

To everyone who always stand by us: thank you for being part of the effort and our collective growth in 2025!

Highlights from 2025

We grew

We consolidated the work of our team and renewed our Advisory Committee to navigate a challenging global landscape strategically.

We empowered

We equipped hundreds of attendees to 4 panels and 2 workshops with resources that build capacities for Latin American researchers.

We co-created

We collaboratively designed and taught a 3-hour workshop on using NASA satellite data for monitoring environmental changes and disturbances.

We showed up

We presented our initiatives and our community at more than 20 regional and international events, reaching a potential audience of over 5,000 attendees.

We joined forces

We established 4 new partnerships with individuals, organizations, and communities, to co-create projects that support local research.

We communicated

We shared the results of our training and research initiatives through 5 scientific publications (2 preprints, 2 posters, and 1 book chapter).

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MetaDocencia nurtures collaboration networks that break down barriers across disciplines, institutions, and countries, elevating Latin American science worldwide.

**Fostering
Community**

We grow through collaboration

20+

events

6

workshops & panels

4

new partnerships

Some featured events

- **NumFOCUS DISC Unconference**
We built knowledge on open practices with people from 16 countries across 5 continents.
- **Global Bioinformatics Education Summit**
We joined training initiatives from all over the world to showcase challenges and learnings from Latin America.
- **Nerdearla**
We joined as Media Partners and showed regional tech communities how we can support their progress.
- **CZI Open Science Meeting**
We hosted a panel with representatives of organizations that fund research, to improve chances of being funded.
- **LABI Meeting**
We supported imaging researchers by running a workshop on accessing funding for scientific initiatives.
- **Ibero-American Open Science Congress**
We raised awareness about Open Science by sharing the results of our training programs and accompanying two art pieces created by our community.

TOGETHER WITH

32

partner communities
& alliances

60+

collaborators

6,000+

people connected

Join our
Slack community

Open and collaborative academic publications

- 'Perceived Barriers for Accessing International Research Funding among Latin American Researchers.' (preprint)
- 'Changes in Knowledge, Practices, and Perceived Importance of Open Science Following a Training Program for Latin American Researchers.' (preprint)
- 'Epistemic Justice and Open Science in Latin America and the Caribbean: The Case of MetaDocencia.' (book chapter)
- 'Positive Impact of a Virtual Open Science Training on Knowledge and the Adoption of Good Practices.' (scientific poster)
- 'Considerations on Open Science from Researchers in the Global South: an Analysis Using NLP Tools.' (scientific poster)

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MetaDocencia creates evidence-based learning programs that turn knowledge into action and new skills into local impact.

Training Researchers

Training in many forms

- **Introduction to the Use of NASA Earthdata Cloud for Monitoring Climate Risks**

In collaboration with 2i2c, we **designed open materials and taught an online course** on how to leverage open Earth Science data and cloud-based interactive computing to reproducibly analyze environmental changes and disturbances.

- **Unlocking Funding for Scientific Initiatives**

At the LABI Meeting, we offered **a workshop** to help improve researchers' chances of securing funding for their scientific projects.

- **Funding as a Tool for a Global and Equitable Open Science**

For the annual CZI Open Science Meeting, we organized **a panel** that explored how funding can transform the way Open Science is developed and shared internationally.

Voices from our community

Marina Compagnucci

Biologist and MetaDocencia contributor, with a key role in the design and adaptation of NASA Open Science content for Latin America.

“ Working with MetaDocencia means proudly being part of **a team that is attentive, warm, diverse, responsible, and committed to its mission and people.** It’s no surprise that creative proposals emerge when dialogue in this space feels natural and reassuring. ”

IN THESE 5 YEARS

97

workshop editions (396 hours)

1,600+

people from 33 countries trained

>85%

Net Promoter Score

Subscribe to our newsletter here
and stay up-up-date with our
training opportunities.

MetaDocencia promotes scientific and technological infrastructure that enables the production, management, and reuse of knowledge.

Enhancing Infrastructure

Better infrastructure, more opportunities

We redesigned our website to show more clearly what we do.

Explore our projects at
www.metadocencia.org

Catalyst Project

We completed a collaborative project that made cloud computing infrastructure more accessible and useful for global life sciences communities.

Contextualization

We develop high-quality Spanish resources for Latin America based on material originally published in other languages.

Equitable Open Peer Review

We collaborate to build Latin American networks that promote open and equitable peer review of preprints and academic datasets.

In 2026, MetaDocencia will continue expanding high-quality training, strengthening open science capacities, and building long-lasting alliances that foster research communities in the region.

Partner with us, fund our initiatives, and help us expand the reach of open, collaborative science in Latin America.

In 2026, we will:

- **Train Latin American researchers in AI Literacy, Open Science, and with Train-the-Trainer programs**
- **Build and strengthen Latin American communities to improve access to research funding**
- **Advance Latin American research infrastructure through rigorous research and openly sharing all our outputs**

Thank you!

Our heartfelt thanks to the 6,000+ people who engage with, contribute to, and amplify our work, and the dozens of institutions and organizations that have invested in our mission since 2020.

CS&S

Code for
Science & Society

Chan Zuckerberg
Initiative

NASA
Open Science

Latin America
Bioimaging

UNC
Supercómputo

2i2c

Invest in Open
Infrastructure

PREREVIEW
PREREVIEW

<ReSA>

Research Software Alliance

Research
Software
Alliance

Ersilia

Openlab

EMBL Bio-IT

EMBL
Bio-IT

Open
Knowledge
Foundation

ILDA

Iniciativa
Latinoamericana por
los Datos Abiertos

OLS

Open Research
Community
Accelerator

ARPHAI

ARPHAI

R-Ladies
Buenos Aires

ABRIR

Rede Brasileira de
Reprodutibilidade

FORRT

DiploCientífica

CICADA

SciELO México

SciELO México

Mboa Lab

PsiNet LAB

Arecibo C3

Talarify

Open
Bioinformatics
Foundation

BIH QUEST

Berlin Institute
of Health -
QUEST Center

GORDON AND BETTY
MOORE
FOUNDATION

Gordon and
Betty Moore
Foundation

INTA

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www.metadocencia.org

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